

Identifying uniform DIF in Polytomous Items with LDA

	Current method: WINSTEPS t-test	Proposed method: LDA
statistical significance	Welch t-test $p < 0.0001$	Model comparison χ^2 test $p < 0.0001$
effect size	$abs(contrast) = abs(b_{ref} - b_{foc}) \geq 0.5$	$abs(\hat{\Delta}_{LR}) = abs(-2.35(\hat{\beta}_2)) \geq 1.175$

Uniform DIF using Logistic Discriminant Analysis (LDA)

$$P(G_i | \theta_i, x_i) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\beta_0 - \beta_1 \theta_i)} \quad (1)$$

$$P(G_i | \theta_i, x_i) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\beta_0 - \beta_1 \theta_i - \beta_2 x_i)} \quad (2)$$

G_i is the grouping of candidate i ,

θ_i is the ability of candidate i ,

x_i is the score candidate i obtains.

Identifying uniform DIF in Polytomous Items with LDA

Study design

- Item type
 - Dichotomous item: $b = 0$
 - 4-point polytomous item: $\delta = (-1.5, -0.5, 0.5, 1.5)$
 - 7-point polytomous item: $\delta = (-2.5, -1.2, -0.6, 0, 0.6, 1.2, 2.5)$
- Sample size:
 - Reference: 400
 - Focal: 50, 100, 200, and 400
- Ability distribution difference
 - Reference: $N(0, 0.25)$
 - Focal: $N(0, 0.25)$, $N(-0.5, 0.25)$, and $N(0.5, 0.25)$
- DIF size
 - Type I error rate: 0
 - Power: 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 1

100 repetitions

Identifying uniform DIF in Polytomous Items with LDA

Results

- Type I error rate of both WINSTEPS and LDA are controlled at nominal level.
- When DIF size is small (0.3), the power is around 0.02.
- Aggregated results for DIF size 0.5, 0.7, and 1.

LDA is generally comparable to the currently used WINSTEPS in DIF detection type I error and power rates. Utilizing LDA can avoid the asymmetry issue of WINSTEPS in terms of ability distribution.